

STABILITY OF COMPRESSIVE RESIDUAL STRESSES IN AUSTEMPERED DUCTILE IRON (ADI) UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

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Compressive residual stresses induced by deep rolling can effectively reduce crack initiation and crack growth in the surface layer of high strength cast components. The result is an intended increase in fatigue strength. In this study, compressive residual stresses were induced in the austempered ductile iron GJS 800-8 by deep rolling. The influence of the residual stresses was investigated on notched round specimens under cyclic loading at constant load amplitudes and R-ratio. In the deep-rolled notch radius depth profiles of the near surface residual stresses were mapped using the $\cos\alpha$ method. The test results show a relaxation of the compressive residual stress depending on the stress amplitude. The applicability of the $\cos\alpha$ method for ADI was confirmed by reference measurements using the hole-drilling method.

Keywords: compressive residual stress, $\cos\alpha$ method, deep rolling, austempered ductile iron

INTRODUCTION

Residual stresses are caused by many technically relevant manufacturing, machining and treatment processes and influence material properties in many ways. Under mechanical load, the existing residual stresses are superimposed on the load stresses in an additive manner. The effects of residual stresses play a decisive role in the fatigue behaviour of metallic materials, especially in areas close to the surface which are critical to failure.

To increase the durability of high strength cast components, mechanical surface treatment processes, e.g. deep rolling, are often used in practice. The compressive residual stresses induced by this process can effectively reduce crack initiation and crack growth in the surface layer of the component and thus result in an intended increase in fatigue strength, especially in the case of safety-relevant components. These macro residual stresses are always the result of inhomogeneous plastic deformations and/or phase transformations. The plastic deformation of the surface layer is interfered by the underlying component core, which is only elastically deformed. The compressive residual stresses in the surface layer are caused by the load relief of the component core. This means that the compressive residual stresses are in equilibrium with the tensile residual stresses underneath. Depending on whether the process of Hertzian compression (force effect perpendicular to the surface) or the material stretching at the surface (force effect perpendicular and parallel to the surface) dominates, the greatest deformations occur directly at or below the surface. Consequently, the maximum residual stresses also occur directly at or below the material surface [1, 2].

In the present study, compressive residual stresses were induced in the high strength and at the same time tough austempered ductile iron (ADI) by deep rolling. ADI is superior to conventional grades of spheroidal graphite cast iron according to DIN EN 1563 [3] in terms of strength and

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plasticity. The static and dynamic properties of ADI are comparable to those of quenched and tempered steels. The influence of the residual stresses was investigated on notched round specimens under tension-compression loading at constant stress amplitude and constant R-ratio. The determination of the residual stresses near the surface before and after the cyclic loading was carried out via X-ray diffraction using $\cos\alpha$ method. In contrast to the widely used $\sin^2\Psi$ method, the advantages are shorter measuring times and better component accessibility by mobile X-ray technique for measurement in critical areas, as here in the deep-rolled notch radius. Electrolytic material removal at the measuring spot was used to map the depth profile of the residual stresses close to the surface. Reference measurements were carried out on flat samples in deep-rolled and untreated state using the hole-drilling method.

The effect of the compressive residual stresses is only maintained until they are relieved. In this case the compressive residual stresses in the highly stressed notch root are superimposed with tensile stresses that are above the yield point. The test results show that the stability of the compressive residual stresses depends on the applied stress amplitude. A significant reduction of the compressive residual stresses induced by deep rolling was only found at a higher stress amplitude in the region of high cycle fatigue. A comparison of the residual stress profiles from measurements using X-ray diffraction and hole-drilling method confirms that the $\cos\alpha$ method fits well for ADI.

Two problems are to be analysed with the research presented here:

- knowledge of the residual stress distribution after deep rolling of ADI castings and their stability under cyclic loading as an important element in estimating component durability
- examining the applicability of the $\cos\alpha$ method for determining the residual stress depth distribution on heterogeneous spheroidal cast iron.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Test material

The heat treatment of the GJS 600 alloy castings to produce ADI grade GJS 800-8 was carried out in one batch at ADI Treatments Ltd (West Bromwich, England). For uniform austenitisation and carbon saturation of the austenite, the as-cast blanks were heated to 870 °C, kept at this temperature for three hours, and then quenched to 380 °C. The isothermal transformation temperature was maintained for 60 min until the structural transformation of austenite into ausferrite was completed. Afterwards, the cast samples were cooled down to room temperature. The resulting ausferritic microstructure is a mixture of acicular ferrite and stabilised austenite, which ensures the high strength and ductility of the ADI. The chemical composition and mechanical properties are listed in Tables 1 and 2. A graphite analysis according to DIN EN ISO 945 [4] showed that the spheroidal graphite in the ADI structure with the predominant spherulite sizes 6-8 and a proportion of graphite form VI of 78 % meets the usual requirements for GJS. The metallographic austenite analysis showed a content of 33 %.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of GJS 800-8

C (%)	Si (%)	Mn (%)	P (%)	S (%)	Cu (%)	Ni (%)	Cr (%)
3.64 – 3.72	2.26 – 2.37	0.28 – 0.32	0.012 – 0.14	0.005 – 0.009	0.77 – 0.82	0.75 – 0.82	0.06 – 0.17

TABLE 2 Mechanical properties of GJS 800-8

Yield strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Hardness (HRC)
711	1006	11	33

Deep rolling

A hydrostatic tool (*ECOROLL*) was used for the deep rolling of the ADI specimens. For the rolling tests in this study, a rolling force of 750 N (rolling pressure 300 bar) was applied. Deep rolling of the tension-compression fatigue specimens was carried out on a conventional lathe from *TRENS-TREŇČIN* in the notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm. Fig. 1 shows the specimen geometry and orientation. After deep rolling, the surface roughness was determined in the notch radius.

In addition, plate-shaped specimens (155x17x6 mm) were processed using the same rolling force on a conventional milling machine (*INTOS*). These are used for comparative investigations of the residual stress state using $\cos\alpha$ and hole drilling method.

FIGURE 1 Tension-compression fatigue specimen with notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm.

Fatigue testing

To determine the fatigue behaviour of the ADI grade GJS 800-8 after deep rolling, comprehensive fatigue tests were carried out at constant stress amplitudes and a constant stress ratio $R = -1$. As the fatigue test results of cast materials can scatter considerably, 45 specimens were examined in the untreated and deep-rolled (rolling force 750 N) state. The tensile-compression tests were carried out at room temperature and a test frequency of 51 to 53 Hz using a resonance pulsator from *SincoTec*. The limit of number of cycles to failure $N_{f,L} = 2 \times 10^6$ and a frequency difference $\Delta f = \pm 0.1$ Hz as crack starting condition were defined as termination criteria.

Residual stress distribution

The determination of the residual stress distribution near the surface in the deep-rolled specimens before and after the cyclic loading was carried out via X-ray diffraction using $\cos\alpha$ method. The mobile X-ray diffractometer *pulstec μ -X360s* operating by means of $\cos\alpha$ method permits identifying the residual stresses in the notch radius in rolling direction (X , tangential) and transverse to the rolling direction (Y , axial). This method was also applied to the flat specimens in the rolling direction (X , longitudinal) and perpendicular to the rolling direction (Y , transversal) for comparing measurements

with the hole-drilling method. The measuring time for the surface stresses was 5-10 s. Electrolytic material removal at the measuring spot was used to map the depth profiles. The depth steps were set using the etching time. Cast iron can be etched faster than steel. The etching time for 50 μm material removal is 45 s. The actual depth was measured with a micrometer. The resulting etch spot has a diameter of 8 mm. To obtain appropriate results for the cast material ADI, it is necessary to determine the residual stresses for the ferrite and austenite phases separately. The test setup and the two different specimens etched at the notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm (round sample) and in middle of the rolling mark (flat sample) are shown in Fig. 2. The relevant measurement parameters for ferrite and austenite are listed in Table 3.

FIGURE 2 a) Test set up X-ray diffraction, b) flat and c) round specimen with etching spot for determining the residual stress depth profiles.

TABLE 3 Relevant measurement parameters

Parameter	Ferrite	Austenite
measuring spot (mm)	notch radius: 2 / flat sample: 4	
radiation	Cr-K α	
incident angle Ψ_0 (°)	35	30
detector	MAD	
Young's modulus E (GPa)	224	193
Poisson's ratio ν (-)	0.28	0.3
Measured plane	[331]	[200]
tube current (mA)	1.5	

Both, the newer $\cos\alpha$ and the conventional $\sin^2\Psi$ method are based on Bragg's law in equation (1)

$$2d\sin\Psi = \lambda \tag{1}$$

where d is the spacing between the atomic layers, Ψ the incident angle and λ the wavelength of the X-rays. The incident X-rays are reflected at different atomic layers lying in the same direction. A constructive interference will appear, if the reflected X-rays have the same phase. In this case, a signal is detected. Obtaining a constructive interference is only possible at a special incident angle

Ψ . The change of spacing d by applying an external stress is proportional to the resulting macroscopic strain ε . This enables the residual stress to be calculated using the mechanical parameters E and ν . If the material has a polycrystal structure, every X-ray diffraction gives a fully reflected Debye-Scherrer ring at the angle Ψ according to Fig. 3a. Ψ varies depending on the amount of strain. The result is the displacement of the Debye-Scherrer ring [5, 6].

FIGURE 3 Principle $\cos\alpha$ method: a) Debye-Scherrer ring and diffraction angles, b) displacement of the Debye-Scherrer ring under compressive stress [5, 6].

In contrast to $\sin^2\Psi$, for the $\cos\alpha$ method only one incident angle, Ψ_0 , and the displacement of the whole Debye-Scherrer ring, Fig. 3b, is used to analyse residual stresses. If the stress state is without shear, only the ring shifts and the shape remains the same. In the presents of shear stresses the ring is also slightly deformed. In dependence of the rotation angle α the values of the normal and shear residual stresses are given by equations (2) and (3) [5, 6]

$$\sigma_{XX}^{RS} = -\frac{E}{1+\nu} \cdot \frac{1}{\sin 2\eta \sin 2\Psi_0} \cdot \frac{\partial a_1}{\partial \cos \alpha} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{XY}^{RS} = -\frac{E}{1+\nu} \cdot \frac{1}{\sin 2\eta \sin 2\Psi_0} \cdot \frac{\partial a_2}{\partial \sin \alpha} \quad (3)$$

where σ_{XX}^{RS} is the obtained normal stress in the measurement direction, τ_{XY}^{RS} the shear stress, E the Young's modulus and ν the Poisson ratio. Ψ_0 is the incident angle and 2η the angle between the incident and reflected beam, Fig. 3a. The displacement of the Debye-Scherrer ring is defined by the parameters a_1 (only shifting) and a_2 (only deformation) in equations (4) and (5) [5, 6].

$$a_1 = \frac{1}{2} [(\varepsilon_{\alpha} - \varepsilon_{\pi+\alpha}) + (\varepsilon_{-\alpha} - \varepsilon_{\pi-\alpha})] \quad (4)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{2} [(\varepsilon_{\alpha} - \varepsilon_{\pi+\alpha}) - (\varepsilon_{-\alpha} - \varepsilon_{\pi-\alpha})] \quad (5)$$

The two values σ_{XX} and τ_{XY} can be obtained in one measurement. When measuring in four directions ($0^\circ / 180^\circ$ for X direction and $90^\circ / 270^\circ$ for Y direction) and assuming that the residual stress perpendicular to the surface $\sigma_{ZZ}^{RS} = 0$, the entire stress matrix can be calculated. For calculating the normal stress according to (2) in the presents of shear stress, it has to be eliminated by measuring in positive and negative Ψ_0 direction. The mean value of the two results is calculated [5, 6]. Consequently, eight measurements per depth step were required.

For better comparability, the X-ray results for ferrite (σ_F^{RS} , τ_F^{RS}) and austenite (σ_A^{RS} , τ_A^{RS}) were scaled up to ADI 800 using Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio according to equations (6) and (7)

$$\sigma_{ADI}^{RS} = (\sigma_F^{RS} \cdot CF_F \cdot WF_F) + (\sigma_A^{RS} \cdot CF_A \cdot WF_A) \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{ADI}^{RS} = (\tau_F^{RS} \cdot CF_F \cdot WF_F) + (\tau_A^{RS} \cdot CF_A \cdot WF_A) \quad (7)$$

where CF_F and CF_A are the conversion factors for ferrite and austenite, Table 4. The weighting factors WF_F and WF_A depend on the determined austenite and ferrite content of the respective specimen.

TABLE 4 Conversion factors

Parameter	Ferrite	Austenite	ADI 800
Young's modulus E (GPa)	224	193	170
Poisson's ratio ν (-)	0.28	0.3	0.27
$E/(1 + \nu)$ (GPa)	175	148	134
CF (-)	0.77	0.90	-

Reference measurements of the near-surface residual stress distribution were carried out on flat samples in deep-rolled and untreated state using the hole-drilling method. The principle of this method is to drill a hole in a body that is subjected to residual stresses. The stresses are released at the location of the drilled hole. This stress relaxation changes the stress state in the immediate vicinity of the drilled hole. As a result, the local strains in the surface of the test object also change [7]. Using the drilling device RS-200 from *Vishay*, two measurements were done for each specimen in the area of the entire width of the rolling mark or on the reference surfaces. The occurring strains at each drilling depth were measured with special strain gauge rosettes of type CEA-06-062UL-120. Diamond-coated finger cutters with a diameter of 1.6 mm were used for the incremental drilling process. The strain values were recorded up to a depth $z = 0.3$ mm in 20 μm steps and from a depth $z = 0.3$ to 1 mm in 100 μm steps. This depth increments were chosen because the maximum compressive residual stresses due to deep rolling were to be expected in an area directly below the surface. The residual stresses were calculated according to ASTM E837 [8] using the software *H-DRILL* (Hole-Drilling Residual Stress Calculation Program). The integral method applied considers the residual stress gradient varying over the depth after deep rolling.

According to [9], the application of the hole drilling method is suitable in the heterogeneous GJS structure. Reasonable results are achieved up to a ratio of drilling depth/hole diameter $z/D = 0.3$. At greater depths, the inaccuracies increase. With a hole diameter $D = 1.8$ mm used here, this corresponds to a depth $z = 540$ μm . Local microstructural inhomogeneities in the ADI at the measuring point can have a decisive influence on the residual stress value. However, the sign and trend of the residual stresses can be regarded as reality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fatigue strength increase by deep rolling

Fig. 4a shows the S - N values and curves as 50 % survival probability $P_{S,50}(S_a)$ in the deep-rolled (rolling force 750 N) and untreated state for the notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm. The fatigue tests were all

stress-controlled, as only global elastic deformations were expected for the applied loading. The test results in high cycle fatigue (HCF) area at higher stress amplitudes ($S_a = 350\text{-}600$ MPa) were determined using the horizon method. The HCF area close to fatigue limit ($S_a = 250\text{-}340$ MPa) was mapped via stair-step method (stair step = 10 MPa). The statistical evaluation was carried out applying the $\arcsin\sqrt{p}$ transformation. The fatigue strength increase due to deep rolling is much higher in the HCF area at higher stress amplitudes (maximum 1035 % at $S_a = 400$ MPa) than the increase of the fatigue limit (16 %). An explanation can be found in the specimen geometry. The stress concentration factor is $k_t = 1.25$. Due to the low resulting stress gradient in the notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm, an enormous increase in fatigue limit was not expected. However, the Gaussian probability plot for the HCF area close to the fatigue limit in Fig. 4b shows considerable scatter in the deep-rolled versus the untreated state.

FIGURE 4 a) S - N curves of ADI 800 in deep-rolled and untreated state for notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm, b) corresponding Gaussian probability plot for the HCF area close to the fatigue limit.

Deep rolling reduced the surface roughness by 61 %. However, the different roughness in the deep-rolled and untreated state has no influence on the number of cycles to failure, as the internal notch effect (average spherulite size $MaxFerret = 30$ μm) is greater than the external one (maximum roughness depth in the untreated state $R_z = 7$ μm) for this casting material.

A following fracture surface analysis demonstrated the displacement of the location of crack initiation into the specimen interior below the zone of maximum compressive residual stress because of deep rolling. In the untreated state, the fatigue cracks invariably initiated at the surface. Fig. 5 shows an example of each.

FIGURE 5 SEM images of fracture surfaces after the fatigue test: a) crack initiation in the specimen interior due to deep rolling, b) crack initiation at the specimen surface in untreated state.

Initial residual stress distribution after deep rolling

The presented results of the $\cos\alpha$ method were calculated according to equations (2) and (3) for the measurement directions X (tangential, in rolling direction) and Y (axial, transverse to the rolling direction). As shear stress, only the direction with the maximum values, τ_{XY}^{RS} , is given. In addition, the equivalent stress σ_{eq}^{RS} , von Mises, according to equation (8), was determined assuming plane stress. The test results are plotted as residual stress values by depth with the corresponding regression line (3rd degree polynomial).

$$\sigma_{eq}^{RS} = \sqrt{\sigma_{XX}^{RS2} + \sigma_{YY}^{RS2} - \sigma_{XX}^{RS}\sigma_{YY}^{RS} + 3\tau_{XY}^{RS2}} \quad (8)$$

As illustrated in Fig. 6a and 6b, the results of $\cos\alpha$ method show compressive residual stresses due to deep rolling in (σ_{XX}^{RS} , tangential) and transverse to the rolling direction (σ_{YY}^{RS} , axial) over the entire depth considered. While tangentially the maximum compressive residual stresses occur below the surface at a depth of 300 μm , axially they are located directly at the surface. The compressive residual stresses reach higher values axially. From the surface to greater depths, the residual stresses in untreated state change from tensile to compressive range. This stress distribution results from mechanical machining. The shear stress τ_{XY}^{RS} in Fig. 6c is hardly influenced by the deep rolling process. In Fig. 6d the von Mises stresses σ_{eq}^{RS} over the regarded depth are below the yield point in the untreated state (yield point in deep rolled state not determined here but assumed higher). The maximum value for deep rolled state (591 MPa) reaches 83 % of the yield point, the maximum value for untreated state (443 MPa) 62 % of the yield point. Therefore, the residual stresses obtained with the $\cos\alpha$ method are assumed to be valid.

FIGURE 6 Residual stress profiles of ADI 800 after deep rolling (750 N) and in untreated state for notch radius $r_n = 8$ mm: a) tangential normal stress (in rolling direction), b) axial normal stress (transverse to the rolling direction, c) shear stress, d) equivalent stress.

Stability of compressive residual stress under cyclic loading

To investigate the stability of the residual stresses induced by deep rolling under cyclic loading, the depth profiles determined with the $\cos\alpha$ method were compared after deep rolling (without cyclic loading), after reaching fatigue limit as well as after failing in HCF area at higher stress amplitudes. The residual stress distributions in Fig. 7 indicate a dependency on the bearing stress amplitude S_a during cyclic loading. A significant residual stress reduction compared to the unloaded state occurs in the HCF area at $S_a = 600$ MPa, Fig. 7a and 7b. In this case, the compressive residual stresses σ_{XX}^{RS} and σ_{YY}^{RS} are almost constant over the considered depth. Thus, there is no longer a distinct stress maximum. In tangential direction, Fig. 7a, the change of the compressive residual stress compared to the unloaded state occurs relatively uniform for the entire depth range. The stress reduction in axial direction, Fig. 7b, is greatest directly at the surface and decreases sharply to a depth of $350 \mu\text{m}$. At the fatigue limit level ($S_a = 280$ MPa), the compressive residual stresses in rolling direction (σ_{XX}^{RS} , Fig. 7a) initially remain stable up to a depth of $250 \mu\text{m}$ compared to the unloaded state. After that, the residual stress is increasingly reduced. Transverse to the rolling direction (σ_{YY}^{RS} , Fig. 7b), there is a slight reduction in compressive stress up to a depth of $100 \mu\text{m}$ compared to the unloaded state. In the further depth course, the compressive residual stresses continue to decrease gradually, but remain stable compared to the initial deep rolled state. Despite the reduction in residual stress due to cyclic loading, the tangential and axial normal stresses (σ_{XX}^{RS} , σ_{YY}^{RS}) remain in compression range over the depth being considered. The deep rolling effect is still present for all applied stress amplitudes.

Cyclic loading has little influence on shear stress distribution, Fig. 7c. Regardless the stress amplitude, a reduction of τ_{XY}^{RS} compared to the unloaded state can be recognised up to a depth of 200 μm . Dependency on the applied stress amplitude S_a also becomes obvious in the course of the von Mises stresses σ_{eq}^{RS} in Fig. 7d.

FIGURE 7 Residual stress profiles of ADI 800 after deep rolling (750 N) and cyclic loading for notch radius $r_n = 8 \text{ mm}$: a) tangential normal stress (in rolling direction), b) axial normal stress (transverse to the rolling direction), c) shear stress, d) equivalent stress.

Validation of $\cos\alpha$ method for ADI

Fig. 8 compares the results of the $\cos\alpha$ and the hole drilling method (reference measurements on flat specimens) using the rolling force 750 N and the rolling mark spacing 0.4 mm. The results of hole drilling method are given as mean values from the two individual measurements per specimen. The first depth at which values from hole drilling method are plotted is 25 μm , because these values are not directly measurable at the surface and the first and not used value is influenced by surface preparation during strain gauge installation. To better follow the stress courses determined by hole drilling, the values in Fig. 8 are connected with a grey line.

The regression lines of both methods show reasonable deviations for normal (σ_{XX}^{RS} , σ_{YY}^{RS} , Fig. 8a/8b), shear (τ_{XY}^{RS} , Fig. 8c) and von Mises stresses (σ_{eq}^{RS} , Fig. 8d). Differences can be found in the location of the compressive stress maxima. These are shifted both tangentially, Fig. 8a, and axially, 8b, for the hole drilling results to greater depths. The cause is assumed to be inaccuracies in the determination of the depth during local electrolytic material removal ($\cos\alpha$) or in depth adjustment during incremental drilling.

The values of the $\cos\alpha$ method are in the scatter range of the hole drilling values. The residual stresses determined by hole drilling method scatter considerably more than the values of the $\cos\alpha$ method. In compliance with the geometric constraints in [10], the most common sources of error, apart from inaccurate depth adjustment, when using the hole drilling method are as follows

- error during strain measurement,
- measurement error in determining the hole diameter D ,
- error in positioning the strain gauge rosette [10].

The confirmation of the $\cos\alpha$ results using the hole drilling method shows that the $\cos\alpha$ method is suitable to determine the residual stresses in ADI 800.

FIGURE 8 Residual stress profiles of ADI 800 after deep rolling (750 N) for plate-shaped geometry by $\cos\alpha$ and hole drilling method: a) longitudinal normal stress (in rolling direction), b) transversal normal stress (perpendicular to the rolling direction, c) shear stress, d) equivalent stress.

SUMMARY

In this study, compressive residual stresses were induced in the austempered ductile iron GJS 800-8 by deep rolling. Residual stress profiles were determined before and after cyclic loading at different stress amplitudes using the $\cos\alpha$ method. The main results can be summarised as follows:

- The fatigue strength increase due to deep rolling is much higher in the HCF area at higher stress amplitudes than the increase of the fatigue limit.
- The results of $\cos\alpha$ method show compressive residual stresses due to deep rolling in and transverse to the rolling direction over the entire depth considered. While tangentially the

maximum compressive residual stresses occur below the surface at a depth of 300 μm , axially they are located directly at the surface. The compressive residual stresses reach higher values axially. The von Mises stresses before and after deep rolling are below the yield point in the untreated state.

- The residual stress distributions after deep rolling indicate a dependency on the bearing stress amplitude during cyclic loading. A significant residual stress reduction occurs in the HCF area at $S_a = 600$ MPa. In tangential direction the change of the compressive residual stress is relatively uniform for the entire depth range. The stress reduction in axial direction is greatest directly at the surface and decreases sharply to a depth of 350 μm . At the fatigue limit level, the compressive residual stresses in rolling direction initially remain stable up to a depth of 250 μm . After that, the residual stress is increasingly reduced. Transverse to the rolling direction, there is a slight reduction in compressive stress up to a depth of 100 μm . In the further depth course, the compressive residual stresses continue to decrease gradually, but remain stable compared to the initial deep rolled state. Despite the reduction in residual stress due to cyclic loading, the tangential and axial normal stresses remain in compression range over the depth being considered.
- The regression lines of both methods, $\cos\alpha$ and hole drilling, show reasonable deviations for normal, shear and von Mises stresses. Differences can be found in the location of the compressive stress maxima. These are shifted both, tangentially and axially, for the hole drilling results to greater depths. The values of the $\cos\alpha$ method are in the scatter range of the hole drilling values. The confirmation of the $\cos\alpha$ results using the hole drilling method shows that the $\cos\alpha$ method is suitable to determine the residual stresses in ADI 800.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

ADI	austempered ductile iron
MAD	multi-analyser detector
HCF	high cycle fatigue
a_1, a_2	parameters to calculate the displacement of the Debye-Scherrer ring
CF_F, CF_A	conversion factor for ferrite and austenite
D	hole diameter
d	spacing between atomic layers
E	Young's modulus
k_t	stress concentration factor
$MaxFerret$	maximum dimension inside the particle projection
N_f	number of cycles to failure
$N_{f,L}$	limit of number of cycles to failure
$P_{S,50}$	50 % survival probability
R	stress ratio
r_n	notch radius
R_Z	roughness depth

S_a	stress amplitude
WF_F, WF_A	weighting factor for ferrite and austenite
X, Y	measurement direction / specimen orientation
z	drilling depth
Δf	frequency difference (crack starting condition)
ε	macroscopic strain
$\varepsilon_\alpha, \varepsilon_{-\alpha}, \varepsilon_{\pi+\alpha}, \varepsilon_{\pi-\alpha}$	displacement of the Debye-Scherrer ring at four positions
η	half angle between the incident and reflected X-ray beam
λ	wavelength
σ_{eq}^{RS}	equivalent residual stress according to von Mises
$\sigma_{XX}^{RS}, \sigma_{YY}^{RS}, \sigma_{ZZ}^{RS}$	normal residual stress in measurement direction
τ_{XY}^{RS}	shear residual stress in XY direction
ν	Poisson's ratio
Ψ, Ψ_0	incident angle X-ray beam

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